

State defense internalization in a university: Theory of planned behavior approach

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ABSTRACT

Universitas Pembangunan Nasional "Veteran" Jawa Timur (UPNVJT) is a university with state defense education's characters. In practice, those character did not cover the academic field as a whole. Through the theory of planned behavior (TPB), the research carried out the process of internalizing state defense values in thesis writing as a form of character graduates. The research was conducted using a quantitative approach involving stakeholders at UPNVJT, namely LP3M and head of department. Data were analyzed using partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM) software. The results found that two TPB variables, namely attitudes and subjective norms in the organization, had an influence on the intention in implementing state defense values. The intention in implementing state defense values will influence perceived self-efficacy of state defense values. Meanwhile, the subjective norms of the perpetrators and the perception of behavioral control in accordance with the state defense values have no influence on the intention in implementing the state defense values.

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1. INTRODUCTION

State defense is a brand of Universitas Pembangunan Nasional "Veteran" Jawa Timur (UPNVJT). Practically, state defense education is one of university courses that must be taken by all UPNVJT students. The values contained in the state defense is a picture of patriotism in the individual [1]. Although the initial grounding of State defense was drafted, but in the current era of globalization that base needs to be expanded on the ideas of a scientific paper [1]. Various countries have similar programs in an effort to increase the love of homeland. Therefore, UPNVJT as a state defense campus has an important role to foster the spirit of defending the country both physically and mentally [2]. Research conducted by Farida and Azizah [3] stated that the internal brand form can be started from the awareness of UPNVJT employees and lecturers to be able to become role models for students and all relevant stakeholders.

In practice, these characters have not penetrated the academic field such as scientific works based on the values of state defense. This is an interesting thing to strengthen the character of UPNVJT graduates. According to Azizah *et al.* [4], [5], improving an organization's brand is very important starting from the internal side of the organization. Brand internalization, in the context of state defense at UPNVJT has not been carried out optimally because there are still several aspects that have not been based on the values of state defense explicitly [3]. The internalization process in research will focus on a practical approach, where

several previous studies have stated that the approach that is in accordance with the willingness to adopt new habits is theory planned behavior (TPB). TPB is a conceptual framework of several multifaceted variables to describe interesting behavior, namely the involvement and completion of application procedures [6].

The TPB approach in internalizing state defense is used to explore variables related to the willingness to implement [7]. The TPB approach consists of three main variables, namely attitudes, subjective norms and perceptions of behavioral control. Attitudes are positive or negative beliefs about the consequences of performing certain behaviors [8]. Subjective norms are a normative function of a person's beliefs that are approved or disapproved by certain individuals performing certain behaviors. A person will intend to perform a certain behavior when they see it as important which others think they should. Perception of behavioral control is a person's willingness to control when performing a behavior. Perceived behavioral control refers to the degree to which an individual feels that the decision to perform or not perform a behavior is under their volitional control [8].

This research contributes to understanding the process of internalizing state defense from the stakeholders that has been running. The practical approach to policy makers is the first step in changing the behavior of the main actors so that high interest in new habits grows, namely the application of the concept of state defense in the practice of writing the final project. The approach to policy makers is expected to be the first step to build human resources in a structured manner from the policy stage that is made [9]. This is aimed at managing human resources with state defense's characters, so that a legal regulation is needed for the organization [9]. Reed *et al.* stated that the interests and influence of the actors can be understood from the perspective of the actors involved [10].

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. State defense as character of UPNVJT graduates

State defense is an individual's attitude and behavior based on his love for the country which in this case is Indonesia. The essence of the concept of state defense is that citizens are expected to behave and do their best for the country based on the values of state defense. The values of state defense include: i) Love for the homeland, knowing and loving the national territory, always being vigilant, ready to defend Indonesia against all forms of threats; ii) Awareness of the nation and state, always fostering harmony, unity and integrity, always prioritizing the interests of the nation above personal and group interests; iii) Believing in the truth of Pancasila as the philosophy and ideology of the state; iv) Willing to sacrifice for the nation and state; v) Have the initial ability to defend the country [2].

The embodiment of state defense has a broad scope, both military and non-military. One of the implementations of state defense in the non-military scope is the higher education sector which has been applied by Universitas Pembangunan Nasional "Veteran" Jawa Timur. Awareness of defending the state in educational institutions can be done with planned efforts in instilling the values of state defense [11]. Abidin *et al.* stated that the basic values of state defense play an important role in the framework of strengthening existence [2].

2.2. Brand internalization

Branding provides opportunities in the formation of customer perceptions. In addition, branding also represents the relationship between the organization and employees [12]. Branding can be done in three forms, namely: i) Corporate branding; ii) Internal branding; and iii) Employee branding. The three forms have a close relationship where corporate branding focuses on direct relationships with customers while internal branding and employee branding focuses on employees. A study by Vrieling [13] shows that internal branding is seen as an organizational strategy that is able to turn a vision into a brand reality. Furthermore, the study assumes that human resources in the organization play an important role in conveying brand values so that organizational success can be achieved.

The key aspect of applying internal branding lies in the consistency and alignment of employee behavior when interacting with customers [14], [15]. The absence of these aspects lead to the brand vision is not perceived by the customer [12], [16]. The existence of internal branding will contribute to brand-oriented behavior and stimulate employee commitment in carrying out their work activities [17]. Studies conducted by King [18] showed that in general internal branding can increase employee commitment and behavior towards organizations and brands.

King and Grace [12] describes the creation of employee commitment to the brand through several phases. Employees need to be provided with technical information regarding assignments [12]. Employees with access to appropriate brand information will develop a commitment to their work and then develop a strong commitment to the brand itself.

2.3. Theory of planned behavior

The theory of planned behavior (TPB) was proposed by Ajzen to provide a theoretical basis in understanding the behavior of stakeholders in organizations [8]. This theory assumes that individual behavior is driven by behavioral intentions. The behavioral intention is determined by the following three elements: i) Individual attitudes towards behavior; ii) Subjective norms surrounding behavioral performance; iii) Perception of behavioral control [8].

An individual's attitude toward a particular behavior is based on perceptions regarding the outcome of that behavior. This attitude is formed from within the individual which can be taken based on experience or other factors that lead them to predict what will happen. If the predictions and perceived outcomes are positive, individuals will tend to perform the behavior [19]. There are four hypotheses in this study:

H₁: attitude to the values of defending the state will have a positive effect on the interest in implementing the values of defending the state.

Subjective norms that are reflected in the social environment (family, friends, and even the media) also play a role in the individual's intention to behave in a certain way. This subjective norm includes how other people perceive themselves. These norms recommend, motivate, or even pressure individuals to perform these behaviors, as well as how others will react if the individual behaves that way [20]. There are two subjective norms according to TPB, namely subjective norms in actors and subjective norms in organizations [21].

H₂: Subjective norms on the behavior of the values of state defense will have a positive effect on the interest in the application of the values of state defense.

H₃: Subjective norms in organizations that apply the values of state defense will have a positive effect on the interest in implementing the values of state defense.

Individual's perception of behavioral control also has a major impact on the intention to perform a behavior. It relates to the individual's perceived ability to successfully achieve the behavior and the opportunity to perform the behavior consisting of external factors such as time or finance. These three variables have a role in individual intentions. If the individual wants the outcome of the behavior, and external social factors are thought to react positively to the behavior, then the individual will examine their sense of control over the situation and decide whether to perform the behavior or not [22]. The review of the statement becomes the basis for formulating the fourth hypothesis as follows.

H₄: The perception of behavior control that is in accordance with the values of state defense the state will have a positive effect on the interest in implementing the values of state defense.

3. RESEARCH METHOD

This study applied a quantitative approach using a questionnaire as a data collection method. The questionnaire was distributed in a Google Form. The data that has been collected was then analyzed using SmartPLS 3. In this study, the population is less than 100 people, so 100% of the population in LP3M and the head of department at Universitas Pembangunan Nasional "Veteran" Jawa Timur were taken as sample. There were 31 respondents involved in this study. They were consisted of 42% male and 58% female.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The research findings are presented in several segments, namely the validity and reliability of each variable followed by the model. The model explains the influence between the variables used. There are four variables in this study, namely attitudes towards state defense values (S), subjective norms towards perpetrators (NSP), subjective norms towards organizations (NSNO), perceptions of behavior control in accordance with state defense values (PP), interest in apply the values of state defense (M), and behavior that reflects (perceived self-efficacy) the values of state defense (PSE). These variables are measured in several indicators that have been tested for validity and reliability.

The next stage is the reliability test by looking at cronbach alpha (CA), Rho-A, composite reliability (CR) and average variance extracted (AVE). Each indicator has a tress hold value of 0.5 so that if the value of each indicator is more than 0.5, it can be concluded that the tested variables can be declared reliable. Based on the Table 1 and Table 2, the reliability of each indicator item and variable used in this study have been successfully proven.

Table 1. Validity

Items	M	NSO	NSP	PP	PSE	S
M1	0.835					
M2	0.821					
M3	0.903					
M4	0.904					
NSO1		0.751				
NSO2		0.894				
NSO3		0.697				
NSO4		0.751				
NSO5		0.844				
NSP1			0.606			
NSP2			0.694			
NSP3			0.932			
NSP4			0.710			
PP1				0.757		
PP2				0.666		
PP3				0.890		
PP4				0.880		
PP5				0.574		
PP6				0.843		
PSE1					0.819	
PSE2					0.834	
PSE4					0.708	
PSE5					0.742	
PSE7					0.826	
S1						0.699
S2						0.622
S3						0.664
S4						0.825
S5						0.723

Table 2. Reliability

Variables	CA	Rho-A	CR	AVE
M	0.890	0.900	0.923	0.751
NSO	0.858	1.008	0.892	0.625
NSP	0.729	0.791	0.830	0.556
PP	0.863	0.871	0.900	0.604
PSE	0.847	0.849	0.890	0.620
S	0.763	0.776	0.834	0.504

Figure 1 shows that the attitude towards the values of state defense has a significant effect on the interest in implementing the values of state defense. This is in line with the research by Adams and de Kock. They found that the attitude of students at school will affect the interest in applying for work in a particular organization [6].

Meanwhile, the subjective norms of the organization on the interest in implementing the values of state defense have no significant effect on the interest in applying the values of state defense. This result contradicts previous research which stated that organizational subjective norms affect the interest in applying a skill or entrepreneurial spirit [6]. However, Dao *et al.* [23] stated that organizational subjective norms had a weak effect on the interest in implementing entrepreneurship in the context of TPB theory research on engineering and business students on the interest in implementing entrepreneurship.

The third hypothesis in the study shows that the subjective norm of the perpetrators of the values of state defense has a significant effect on the interest in implementing the values of state defense. This is in accordance with several previous studies. They examined student interest in implementing entrepreneurship [24], [25] and students in the fields of engineering and business [23].

Furthermore, the results of the analysis show that the fourth hypothesis is rejected so that the perception of control over the values of state defense does not significantly affect the interest in implementing the values of state defense. Research by Wang and Xu related to the perception of a traveler's control over the selection of environmentally friendly tours also showed similar results [26]. This happens because the respondent feels that there is a lack of control over a phenomenon around him. In this study, it can be implied that controlling behavior in accordance with the values of state defense has a different view from the people in their environment.

The interest in applying the values of state defense has a significant effect on the perceived self-efficacy of the values of state defense. These results are supported by several previous studies that have

several different [6], [24], stating that interest in applying will influence on entrepreneurial behavior. Other supporting studies such as previous research [7]. It interested in implementing environmentally friendly tourism will affect behavior towards the environment that is a tourist destination. The correlation between variables in Figure 1 can be seen in more detail in Table 3.

Based on the results of the research, benefits can be taken that have an impact either directly or indirectly on theoretical and practical science. Theoretically, this research has succeeded in proving that the theory of planned behavior. It is especially on the variables of attitude and subjective norms on the perpetrators that has a significant influence on the interest in applying the values of state defense.

Likewise, the intervening variable of interest in implementing has a significant influence on behavior that reflects the values of state defense. However, not all TPB variables obtained significant results in this study, this could be due to the different research contexts and no similar research has been conducted before. Practically, this research focuses on the application of the branding concept promoted by an organization, namely state defense. Practically, the policy makers in Universitas Pembangunan Nasional “Veteran” Jawa Timur, have subjective attitudes and norms of actors that lead to an interest in applying the values of state defense, and affect behavior in daily life. However, in terms of subjective norms in the organization and perception of control, it still needs to be improved so that these two variables can also influence the interest in implementing and their behavior. So, if at the level of policy makers it has been going well, then the potential for success is applied below, lecturers, students and staff will be more easily accepted and run well.

Figure 1. Research model

Table 3. SmartPLS output

Variable	Original sample	Sample mean	Standard deviation	T statistic	P values
S→M	0.413	0.407	0.195	2.124	0.034
NSO→M	-0.271	-0.232	0.240	1.131	0.259
NSP→M	0.792	0.781	0.141	5.603	0.000
PP→M	0.092	0.074	0.160	0.574	0.566
M→M	0.652	0.656	0.092	7.094	0.000

5. CONCLUSION

This study determined the factors that influence the interest in implementing and behavior that reflects the values of state defense with TPB approach. The results confirmed that two TPB variables, namely attitudes and subjective norms in the organization influenced the intention in implementing state defense values. Based on these results, it is hoped that policy makers pay intention to the variables for internalizing the brand of the state defense at UPNVJT.

This research is still limited to the context of internalizing state defense with the TPB approach and surveys are carried out at the level of policy makers only. So, the results are still very limited and still have the potential to be studied further, related to the application and other theoretical approaches. Suggestions for practitioners or policy makers when internalizing policies would be better initiated and implemented properly by the leadership, so that organizational members can better accept a policy. Suggestions for further research can be explored using other theoretical approaches such as theory acceptance model (TAM), for application in integration in a system and other relevant theories.

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